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Research Article

THE POSTPRANDIAL EFFECT OF PRE MEAL BAR AND DIETARY FIBRE IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

¹Dr Manzoor Hussain, ²Dr. Sundas Mahmood Dar, ³Dr Marwah Mahmood¹Registrar, Medical A unit, MTI/Mardan Medical Complex, Mardan²DHQ Hospital Mandi Bahauddin³WMO, DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan

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Abstract:

Aim: Protein preload improves postprandial glycaemia by animating discharge of insulin and incretion hormones. Notwithstanding, it requires a huge portion of protein to produce a critical impact. The current examination was completed to explore the postprandial glucose-bringing down impact of a primal protein-enhanced, dietary fiber-strengthened bar (PFB), which contains moderate measures of protein, in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus or on the other hand ordinary glucose resilience (NGT). Materials and

Methods: The members (15 sort 2 diabetes mellitus and 15 NGT) were haphazardly appointed to either a premeal or Postmeal PFB gathering and went through two blended feast resistance tests, multi week separated backward request. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from June 2019 to May 2020. Plasma levels of glucose, insulin, glucagon-like peptide-1 and glucose-subordinate insulinotropic polypeptide were estimated.

Results: In mixed-feeding resistance testing, the gradual range below the 0 to 190 min elbow of plasma glucose levels was lower with premeal PFB than with Postmeal PFB in type 2 diabetes mellitus (15,724 - 1,320 mg min/dL vs. 19,643 - 1,368 mg min/dL; P = 0.0003) and NGT members (3,944 - 416 mg min/dL vs. 4,828 - 522 mg min/dL; P = 0.0297). In the type 2 DM members, insulinogenous list and stable elbow zone from 0 to 180 min of plasma, all glucagon-like peptide-1 levels were higher with pre-meal PFB than with post-meal PFB, but not in the NGT members. There was no distinction in the levels of tropical polypeptides of postprandial glucose-subordinate insulin between pre-meal and post-meal BFP in either gathering.

Conclusion: Acute organization of premeal PFB diminished postprandial glucose trip in both sort 2 diabetes mellitus and NGT members. In the sort 2 diabetes mellitus members, pre-meal PFB increased the beginning stage insulin discharge, perhaps through improving glucagon-like peptide-1 discharge.

Keywords: Postprandial, Hypoglycemic Effect, Pre-Meal Bar Enriched, Protein, Dietary Fiber, DM type-2.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Manzoor Hussain,**

Registrar, Medical A unit, MTI/Mardan Medical Complex, Mardan

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Postmeal hyperglycaemia is associated with an increased risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease. Postmeal glucose homeostasis is limited by various factors, such as the amount and organization of supplements, gastric discharge rate, glucose retention rate, discharge of incrementing hormones (glucagon-like peptide-1 [GLP-1] and glucose-subordinate tropical insulin polypeptide [GIP]), insulin discharge, glucose absorption by insulin-sensitive tissues and endogenous glucose production. Understanding these variables allows us to find useful ways to improve postprandial hyperglycaemia and hence its adverse consequences. There is no doubt that alpha-glucosidase inhibitors, which lower postmeal glucose levels, have reduced the risk of creating type 2 diabetes mellitus and major cardiovascular events in people with impaired glucose tolerance. Protein preload has the effect of reducing glucose levels and the tropic of insulin has a subordinate impact on part of the population. Nevertheless, the ideal portion of the protein preload that adjusts the impact of glucose, calorie and cost reduction has not been resolved. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, a protein preload of 50 g of whey reduced postprandial glucose levels by 29% with a doubling of insulin release over a postprandial period of 180 minutes. In a concentrate with Japanese solid limbs, 22 g or 42 g of soy protein disengaged the preload; similarly, postmeal glucose levels decreased with the expansion of insulin secretion. Nevertheless, 50 g of protein compares to 200 kcal, and this abundance of calories can cause different problems, such as weight gain, in some individuals. In a 4-week study of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, a preload of 25 g of whey protein three times daily improved postprandial hyperglycaemia without weight gain. However, the long-term impact of the excess calories provided by the pre-meal protein was not evaluated.

METHODOLOGY:**Figure 1:**

The current survey included 16 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus; in addition, 17 people had NGT. Qualified members were adults aged 19 to 84 years with a body mass index (BMI) of 19.6 to 36.2 kg/m², an expected glomerular filtration rate of ≥ 30 mL/min/1.75 m², and aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase levels near 2.6 which straddle the upper limit of the typical range. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus had been clinically determined to have diabetes mellitus 12 weeks prior to screening and were being treated with lifestyle frameworks or potentially oral antidiabetic drugs, including metformin, sulfonylurea and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor, as monotherapy or as combination therapy. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from June 2019 to May 2020. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus had an HbA1c level of 8.7-13.1 percent if they had never seen a glucose control specialist, and an HbA1c level of 7.1-12.0 percent if they had never seen a glucose control specialist, 1% if they had taken metformin or a sulfonylurea and an HbA1c level of 7.1 to 8.1% if they had taken a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor in combination therapy for 12 weeks prior to randomization. The NGT members were never known to have diabetes mellitus, with fasting blood glucose <100 mg/dl and HbA1c <6.0% as reported by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence Guidance for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus²⁶ at the time of testing. Members who were determined to have type 1 diabetes mellitus or diabetic ketoacidosis; who were on insulin therapy; and who had a history of sensitivity to flour, nuts, vegetables and milk were screened out; who had a history of gastrointestinal medical procedure experiences (in addition to hemorrhoidectomy, hernia set procedure and appendectomy); and women who were pregnant or otherwise breastfeeding. The investigation agreement was confirmed by the governing body of the institutional investigation of the Seoul State University Hospital (IRB No. 1307-133-508). All members gave informed and composed consent.

Figure 2:

RESULTS:

A total of 31 members were monitored for the current investigation, however, one member with NGT was avoided due to fasting hyperglycemia. Finally, 30 members (15 members with type 2 diabetes mellitus and NGT, individually) completed the concentrate without adverse events, including gastrointestinal manifestations. For members with type 2 diabetes mellitus, normal age was 63.8 to 4.5 years, BMI was 25.9 to 4.6 kg/m² and HbA1c was 6.9 to 0.5%. The mean duration of type 2 diabetes mellitus was 14.9 to 7.8 years, and all type 2 diabetics were taking an oral antidiabetic drug, including metformin, anyway. Among NGT members, normal age was 48.4 to 8.9 years, BMI was 24.2 to 4.2 kg/m² and HbA1c was 6.4 to 0.4%. Table 2 provides additional data on laboratory test side effects and clinical history. In members of type 2 diabetes mellitus, the iAUC0-180 of plasma glucose levels, which was the primary

endpoint of this study, was lower overall with pre-meal PFB than with post-meal PFB (14,727 - 1,320 mg min/dL vs. 19,642 - 1,367 mg min/dL, $P = 0.0002$; Figure 2c). Post-meal plasma glucose levels would generally be lower with pre-meal PFB than with post-meal PFB in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus (Figure 2a). In the NGT group, iAUC0-180 plasma glucose levels were essentially lower with pre-meal than with post-meal PFB (3,943 - 416 mg min/dL vs. 4,827 - 520 mg min/dL, $P = 0.0297$; Figure 2c). Plasma glucose levels were essentially lower with pre-meal PFB than with post-meal PFB at 30 min (123 - 4 mg/dL vs. 146 - 5 mg/dL, $P = 0.002$) and 60 min (118 - 5 mg/dL vs. 139 - 7 mg/dL, $P = 0.008$) after a NGT investigative dinner (Figure 2b). Pre-meal PFB did not influence plasma glucose levels 0 min in members with type 2 diabetes mellitus or NGT (Figure 2a, b).

Table 1:

Characteristic	Value
Age, yr	31.4± 8.6
Male sex	14 (70)
Height, cm	168.9± 8.8
Weight, kg	67.4± 12.2
BMI, kg/m ²	23.6± 3.9
Systolic BP, mm Hg	117.7± 12.2
Diastolic BP, mm Hg	75.4± 10.1
Fasting glucose, mmol/L	4.92± 0.55
HbA1c, %	5.2± 0.3
Total cholesterol, mmol/L	4.84± 0.95
Triglyceride, mmol/L	0.94± 0.46
HDL-C, mmol/L	1.54± 0.43
LDL-C, mmol/L	2.99± 1.04
AST, IU/L	18.3± 6.6
ALT, IU/L	19.8± 12.4
Creatinine, μmol/L	79.6± 17.7
Estimated GFR	98.2± 18.3

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation or number (%).
 BMI, body mass index; BP, blood pressure; HbA1c, glycosylated he-

Table 2:

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF ENERGY INTAKE

Energy intake	Premeal type			ANOVA	P value		
	Water	UB	PFB		Water vs. UB ^a	Water vs. PFB ^a	UB vs. PFB ^a
Total energy intake 0–30 min, kcal	713.5±219.1	738.5±294.3	666.5±327.5	0.161	NA	NA	NA
Test meal intake 0–30 min, kcal	713.5±219.1	665.5±294.3	593.5±327.5	<0.001	0.198	0.041	0.041
Total energy intake 0–120 min, kcal	1,075.0±508.0	1,013.1±499.3	904.4±534.9	0.008	0.471	0.016	0.078
Test meal intake 0–120 min, kcal	1,075.0±508.0	940.1±499.3	831.4±534.9	<0.001	0.044	0.001	0.078
Water intake	526.0±190.2	541.5±273.5	544.0±237.9	0.922	NA	NA	NA

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation.

UB, usual bar; PFB, protein-enriched dietary fiber-fortified bar; ANOVA, analysis of variance.

^aP value was calculated by Tukey's *post hoc* analysis when the P for ANOVA was <0.05.

Figure 2:

DISCUSSION:

We found that pre-meal PFB decreased postprandial glucose output after a standard test feast in type 2 diabetes mellitus or NGT members [6]. Previously, a single 50 g serving of whey protein or a 4-week treatment with 25 g of whey protein three times daily improved Postmeal hyperglycaemia when given before a mixed meal. In any case, weight gain due to excess calories can be an expected problem from burning a huge amount of protein before a meal [7]. In a portion response study, 10 g, 20 g and 40 g of whey protein preload reduced the glycemic response by 20%, 48% and 66%, separately, after burning a 13 kcal/kg body weight pizza¹⁵. Since the impact of protein preload on glucose reduction is dependent on the serving size, it is essential to decide on the base serving size of the protein. To avoid the postprandial impact of glucose lowering while decreasing the protein measure [8], we added dietary fiber (12.7 g) to the protein (12.8 g) in bar form. In general, it was

found that the intake of PFB before meals improved the Postmeal glycemic response in members of type 2 diabetes mellitus or NGT diabetes mellitus. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, the impact of pre-meal PFB on blood glucose reduction was related to an expansion of early-phase insulin release, manifested by an enlarged IGI and leftward movement in the elbow of plasma insulin during TMD [9]. In contrast, Postmeal insulin discharge during TTME was lower with premeal FPB than with Postmeal FPB. These findings mean that early insulin release is more fundamental to the control of Postmeal hyperglycaemia than total insulin release [10].

CONCLUSION:

Taking all this into account, the intense pre-meal planning of PFB improved postprandial glucose travel in members with type 2 diabetes mellitus and NGT. While the instrument of activity and long-term impact need to be explored, PFB could be a non-

pharmacological approach to improving postmeal glucose digestion.

REFERENCES:

1. Gunnerud UJ, Ostman EM, Bjorck IM. Effects of whey proteins on glycaemia and insulinaemia to an oral glucose load in healthy adults; a dose-response study. *Eur J Clin Nutr* 2013; 67: 749–753.
2. Kashima H, Uemoto S, Eguchi K, et al. Effect of soy protein isolate preload on postprandial glycemic control in healthy humans. *Nutrition* 2016; 32: 965–969.
3. Mignone LE, Wu T, Horowitz M, et al. Whey protein: the “whey” forward for treatment of type 2 diabetes? *World J Diabetes* 2015; 6: 1274–1284.
4. Kuwata H, Iwasaki M, Shimizu S, et al. Meal sequence and glucose excursion, gastric emptying and incretin secretion in type 2 diabetes: a randomised, controlled crossover, exploratory trial. *Diabetologia* 2016; 59: 453–461.
5. Jenkins DJ, Wolever TM, Leeds AR, et al. Dietary fibres, fibre analogues, and glucose tolerance: importance of viscosity. *Br Med J* 1978; 1: 1392–1394.
6. Bergmann JF, Chassany O, Petit A, et al. Correlation between echographic gastric emptying and appetite: influence of psyllium. *Gut* 1992; 33: 1042–1043.
7. Raben A, Tagliabue A, Christensen NJ, et al. Resistant starch: the effect on postprandial glycemia, hormonal response, and satiety. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1994; 60: 544–551.
8. Kim EK, Oh TJ, Kim LK, et al. Improving effect of the acute administration of dietary fiber-enriched cereals on blood glucose levels and gut hormone secretion. *J Korean Med Sci* 2016; 31: 222–230.
9. Silva FM, Kramer CK, de Almeida JC, et al. Fiber intake and glycemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a systematic review with meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Nutr Rev* 2013; 71: 790–801.
10. Clifton PM, Galbraith C, Coles L. Effect of a low dose whey/ guar preload on glycemic control in people with type 2 diabetes—a randomised controlled trial. *Nutr J* 2014; 13: 103.